

Data Pitch

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D4.1 Call definition

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Abstract

This deliverable gives a summary of the artifacts that were produced in the context of the 2017 call of Data Pitch. This includes the call announcement, the guide for applicants and related documents, the submission platform, and application support instruments which will help startups and SMEs understand what it is expected from them and how to improve their applications.

Executive summary

This is the first deliverables of WP4 Competitive call. This is the work package that implements the competition by which Data Pitch selects the startups and SMEs that will be accepted into the data accelerator run by WP5. WP4 also has tied to WP3, which delivers the challenges that the startups and SMEs will respond to, as well as the data catalog for the data provider challenges; to WP2, which helps applicants and data providers with technology and hosting capabilities; and to WP6, which helps spread the word about the competition. WP4 consists of the following tasks:

4.1	Call definition and documentation
4.2	Submission platform
4.3	Relationship to applicants and datathons
4.4	Applications review
4.5	Call dashboard

This document is the summary of all activities carried out in tasks T4.1 to T4.4 in the first six months of the project. We will report on the results of the first call via a dashboard delivered by task T4.5, which will be delivered as part of D4.2 Summary of round 1.

Overview of the activities and outputs in each task

Task 4.1: Call definition and documentation

The entry point for each application is the application page at <https://datapitch.eu/apply/>

It lists the main steps and points to relevant documentation and the submission platform.

The reference documents for participating in the call are the guide for applicants, which can be found at https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9IIZV_CjqLcOTVIYkh6V0xGNE0/view?pli=1 and the challenges, which are published online at <https://datapitch.eu/challenges/> and available for download at https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B9IIZV_CjqLceGVudWlLcWN4M0k.

Each challenge also has its dedicated page, as shown for example, at <http://datapitch.eu/challenges/dpc1-2017/> for the Sonae's supply chain management challenge. For each challenge we list the organisation(s) that helped us define it, as well as relevant datasets and expected outcomes and impacts.

data·pitch
INNOVATION PROGRAMME

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 RETAIL

Future-proof retail supply chains

Challenge identifier: DPC1-2017

Proposed by
Sonae, a Portuguese retail company, with around 40,000 employees and offices in more than 60 countries.

Description
The McKinsey 2014 report 'Global flows in a digital age' lists supply chain management as one of the four core factors for the success of the digitisation strategy of any business. With supply chain data innovation, improved data services, control, and reporting mechanisms can be created, enabling more advanced reporting and planning. Not only does this support key business activities, it also creates better resilience, data governance, and increasing transparency to partners.

Supply chain optimization is vital to run a business with lower stock holdings and to minimize the lost sales that are due to stock outs (not having products available in the shelves); to Sonae these are critical business metrics. Supply chains of perishables to multiple locations are particularly sensitive to a variety of internal (transport, storage) and external (weather, tastes) factors. The challenge proposed here is to precisely design the supply chain graphs considering future promotional activity, in order to not only avoid stock outs but also minimize logistic costs.

Data
Sonae will share data about product flows between locations, stored as a single, large denormalized table with the challenge winners. The data is created using Sonae's operational systems and collected on their premises in a data warehouse. It is made available to third parties via Amazon AWS S3/Redshift. For the purpose of the experiments, the data cannot be stored outside the EU, although locations such as AWS Ireland and Germany are acceptable.

[More detailed information about the data can be found in our data catalogue.](#)

Expected outcomes

- Algorithms and tools for data analysis, reporting, and visualisation, which help Sonae identify areas of improvement within their supply chain.
- Prediction algorithms that help decrease total stock holdings and lost sales.
- Supply chain optimisation algorithms, including algorithms that help decrease product waste and lead to better carbon footprints.

Expected impacts

- Decrease total stock holdings by 10% and stock outs (lost sales) by 20% by better predicting and optimizing the supply chain needs.
- Achieving these KPIs will have a direct impact of product waste decrease and less CO2 emissions.

Data provider challenges also link to the Data Pitch data catalog, which collects metadata about the datasets, links to further documentation etc. This data catalog is part of WP3. The figure below shows the dataset information for the Sonae challenge.

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INNOVATION PROGRAMME

Sonae supply chain data (DPC1-2017)	
BIG DATA, LOGISTICS, RETAIL, SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT	
Published: June 26, 2017	Provider: Sonae (Portugal)
<p>Description</p> <p>Supply chain data. One huge denormalized table with one line per product flow between locations. These type of datasets, though format specific to Sonae, are general data sets for the retail sector. All the datasets are created in our operational systems, collected in our on premises data warehouse, and made available to 3rd parties through Amazon AWS S3 Redshift.</p>	
<p>Industry sector</p> <p>Retail</p>	
<p>Data Provider Country</p> <p>Portugal</p>	
<p>Updates</p> <p>The dataset used in the experiment will have a biweekly update frequency to be decided with the challenge winner.</p>	
<p>Dataset Size</p> <p>20TB of compressed data (1/10 ratio)</p>	
<p>Number of attributes</p> <p>> 120</p>	
<p>Format and storage</p> <p>CSV files stored in Amazon AWS</p>	
<p>Attributes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transactional data - One denormalized table with one line per item sold in our stores, includes information about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data/time Product Store Customer (unique hash/id only) Applied promotions Priced Supply chain data - One denormalized table with one line per product flow between locations 	
<p>Personal data</p> <p>No data relating to persons present</p>	
<p>Synthetic Data</p> <p>No Synthetic data present</p>	
<p>Geographic coverage</p> <p>Portugal</p>	
<p>Timespan & Production</p> <p>Timespan: Jan 2017 - present Production: live</p>	
<p>Level of aggregation</p> <p>Raw data</p>	
<p>Data access</p> <p>Bulk download</p>	

In the guide for applicants we provide pointers to all supporting documents applicants need to be aware of when preparing their application

- a short proposal template, including instructions on how to complete each section, available at <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1vowR9QBZqj7nePIM7tFJ-e-K4PqmvSYMYjhFvlpk5xl>
- the declaration of honour and ethics statement each applicant need to sign, both available at https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/0B9IIZV_CjqLcQVRnOWk0WUVjc3M
- a template of the SME contract which successful applicants will sign with Data Pitch, available at <https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B9fO1KgpJgo1TEx2NGJwVC1WQ2c>; and
- a template for the work plan template, which will define the main outputs of each funded project, available at https://drive.google.com/open?id=1A6nNzxi6Hb4jUhl3bBh4IxbH4Fw_DCPq4VLVie-yaPA

Task 4.2 Submission platform

The submission platform is available at <https://www.f6s.com/datapitchaccelerator/apply>.

Besides basic information similar to the datapitch.eu/apply/ page, it consists of four parts:

- basic information about the applicant, including PIC and relationship to data provider.
- links to declaration of honour and ethics statement.
- short proposal (online form and 1 minute video about the team)

- additional documentation (a pitch deck and, if relevant, proof of access to datasets for those applications that target a sector challenge or the open innovation challenge).

The screenshot shows the Data Pitch Accelerator 17/18 application page. The header includes the Data Pitch logo and the text 'Data Pitch Accelerator 17/18 Helping startups and SMEs innovate with data'. The navigation bar has 'About', 'Discuss', 'Application', and '13 Connections'. The main content area includes a sidebar with 'Apply by Oct 1 '17', 'Feb 1-Jul 31 '18 (6 months)', and 'data-pitch INNOVATION PROGRAMME'. The main content area has a 'Let's get started' section with a 'CREATE TEAM' button, a 'Questions' section with a lock icon, and a 'General guidelines' section with a 'Section 1: Select a Challenge' form.

T4.3 Relationship to applicants and datathons

We have set up an email address call@datapitch.eu for applicants to answer questions about the Data Pitch call. It is advertised on the Web site, in the guide for applicants and on the submission platform.

We have also collected an initial list of FAQs and published them on our Web site at <https://datapitch.eu/faq/> with a variety of questions related to access to data, selecting the most relevant challenges, eligibility, budget etc.

We will organise several online webinars to respond to questions about the call and the datasets it involves, once a month in July, August and September 2017.

To scout interesting applications and allow potential candidates to learn more about the call and its data we have been involved or will be involved in several datathons:

- A datathon together with the Deutsche Bahn, on May 12th - 14th in Berlin. The report is available at <https://datapitch.eu/news/data-pitch-hacks-its-way-to-berlin/>
- A business hackathon oriented towards data-driven innovation in mobility on June 9th - 11th, in Berlin. The report is available at <https://datapitch.eu/news/data-pitch-and-comtrade-digital-services-come-together-for-mobility-business-hackathon/>
- A hackathon around retail and supply chain data, supported by our partner Sonae and organised by Beta-i in Lisbon, September 28th - 30th, as part of PixelsCamp, see <https://pixels.camp/>.

T4.4 Applications review

As part of the call, we have provided information about the review process in the guide for applicants (see How do we select companies?) including detailed scoring criteria (see Annex 6 of the guide). The guide also gives details on the schedule of the reviews, with notifications for shortlisted companies by October 16th and interviews in London in the week commencing October 30th.

Reviews will be documented via F6S. Shortlisted companies will be invited to interviews and receive feedback.